

What is the Deliberative Education Model for First-Time Voters that Meets the Expectations of First-Time Voters

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Abstract:- This study aims to produce a deliberative education model for first-time voters that meets the expectations of first-time voters. The research method used in this study is a mixed methods approach with research data obtained from questionnaires using the Google form, interviews and completed with Focus Group Discussion (FGD). The data analysis technique uses the Mixed Method Data Analysis process determined by sequential mixed analysis. The results of data analysis and findings showed that the level of knowledge of many respondents was in the medium category (36.31%) and the lowest was in the very low category (3.42%). Furthermore, the willingness of novice voters to choose is very high, reaching 90.41% in the High category. In the aspect of political education that is expected by novice voters from the initial analysis, namely the desire for political education for those who put more emphasis on justice, there is no doctrine or the interests of certain groups, true democracy, enlightens voters, especially about a complete understanding in order to change people's mindsets so that they are more good about politics needed in social life. Conclusions and suggestions for future research that the political knowledge of novice voters in Batu city is sufficient.

Keywords:- Education Model; Deliberative; Beginner Selector.

I. INTRODUCTION

In Indonesia, the implementation of civic political education has not run optimally. This kind of reality is influenced by the history of poor citizens' perspectives on political functionality in the life of the nation and state. In the pre-reformation era, politics was more likely to be used as an instrument by the ruling regime to maintain its status quo than to fight for the realization of a just and prosperous social order as mandated by Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution.

After the reform, elections were carried out 5 times, however, the number of abstentions (not using voting rights) increased in 4 general elections (elections for legislative members) and presidential elections (elections for president and vice president) [5]. In the 2019 elections, the number of first-time voters has increased but they have not participated optimally. In line with the Executive Director of the Association for Elections and Democracy (Perludem) that

the number of first-time and young voters in the 2019 elections reached around 14 million. Large numbers will influence legislative candidates and presidential candidates to be able to win the hearts of young voters

The social construction of this unhealthy political practice has not been completely eliminated until now. In the post-reform era which is determined to improve the quality of deliberative democracy, the role and function of political education is very vital for the success of Indonesia's national political development. More political education is needed by the younger generation (youth), especially those who do not study scientifically in the field of political science. This is because they have not received adequate political education, either from the family, community or school environment. Another consideration is because they are candidates for the nation's next generation, so that with qualified political knowledge, they will later be able to contribute to the national political structure critically, constructively,

The more space and time available for the younger generation to receive political education, the more wide open it will be for the birth of a golden generation of the nation capable of developing national political practices, not mere power politics. social media so that they believe in hoax news (news, information, fake or fake news). This then makes the younger generation more apathetic by being abstentions. Not to mention the issue of SARA which is still popping up on social media creating public unrest. Member of the Supreme Council for Confucianism in Indonesia (Matakin) Ung Sendana said that issues regarding ethnicity, race, religion and inter-group (SARA) were still a problem in Indonesia. According to Ung, This problem will have a negative impact on the life of a pluralistic society. An example is the case of violence in Papua [6]. It should (das sollen), the younger generation have an attitude of no Hoax, no SARA, no Abstentions and also tolerance yes, democracy yes and Pancasila yes. From the description above, the problem can be formulated as follows: "What is the deliberative education model for first-time voters that meets the expectations of first-time voters?" Then the urgency of this research is the importance of finding a model of political education (1) for novice voters that is in accordance with the characteristics of the millennial generation with an adequate understanding of deliberative. From the description above, the problem can be formulated as follows: "What is the deliberative education model for

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II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. State of the Art

One of the results of research conducted by Vina SD Soedarwo and Wahyudi shows that constituents from politicians have knowledge about nationalism and political knowledge is still low. The cause of the waning of nationalism in constituents is caused by the lack of socialization processes about nationality/statehood, people only have high tension in the state/nationality only when there are political gawe (activities) such as Pilkada, Pileg, and Presidential Election. The results of this study recommend the existence of a participatory integrative model of political education that involves not only political parties but also universities [7]. Subsequent research has found that the reality of the political education model within political parties is that not all of them are programmed periodically. as well as the finding that political knowledge of voters in general elections in Indonesia is still low.[8]. Political education is a very important thing to do in increasing the participation of first-time voters (17-24 years old) including university students. The results of the research conducted by Fernanda [9] on the Perceptions of Beginner Voters Against Simultaneous Regional Elections in Way Mili Village showed that the perceptions of novice voters towards indicators of understanding simultaneous regional elections were 58.92% with the category tending to not understand. The results of this study are in line with the study conducted by Hajad & Ikhsan which shows that the political participation of young voters in elections is strongly influenced by the level of knowledge, understanding, and literacy (political literacy) possessed by first-time voters. Prior to the activity, the results of the pre-test knowledge of the 57 students, 25, while after getting political education the average score rose to 70.25. Thus, there is an increase in students' knowledge regarding political participation [10].

The results of another study by Ratnamulyani and Mintai illustrate the role of social media in increasing the political participation of first-time voters in Bogor Regency. The results of the study draw conclusions: 1) Politicians in Bogor Regency have not been able to optimize the use of internet-based social media applications for campaign purposes in order to increase the participation of first-time voters from among students, 2) Politicians are less able to take advantage of the potential of first-time voters among

students who are the majority already have social media accounts for the benefit of legislative election campaigns in Bogor Regency, 3) Using social media account facilities is not considered urgent, and 4) In general, the content (content) of campaign messages published on social media lacks appeal. Because the content (content) of the packed campaign does not match the characteristics of novice voters among students [11]. Research on political education among first-time voters was also conducted by Nina Angelia at SMA 1 Percut Sei Tuan Deli Serdang. This study aims to determine the knowledge of students as first time voters about the function of political education. The research results show that political education can: 1) increase knowledge about democratic values, the quality of the electoral process, and political participation; and 2) useful in providing clear information about the functions of elections, as well as the use of voting rights [12]. This study aims to determine the knowledge of students as first time voters about the function of political education. The research results show that political education can: 1) increase knowledge about democratic values, the quality of the electoral process, and political participation; and 2) useful in providing clear information about the functions of elections, as well as the use of voting rights [12]. This study aims to determine the knowledge of students as first time voters about the function of political education. The research results show that political education can: 1) increase knowledge about democratic values, the quality of the electoral process, and political participation; and 2) useful in providing clear information about the functions of elections, as well as the use of voting rights [12].

B. Integrative Participatory Deliberative Democracy

Etymologically the word deliberation comes from the Latin word *deliberatio* which means consultation, deliberation or deliberation which can be interpreted as a form of government in which decisions are made in a country that are passed not according to group or one member of the community. In general, there are two models of democracy, namely direct democracy and indirect democracy. Kelsen stated that direct democracy is democracy with the highest degree, seen from the fact that the laws that are enacted can be implemented or implemented by the people in general meetings or large gatherings and this principle can be implemented by people who are in simple social conditions. The model of indirect democracy or representative democracy, namely the difference lies in the conditions and the development of human civilization which create conditions when collective consensus is not possible in the life of the state. The function of forming legislation is transferred from citizens to a representative democracy model that does not place constituents in the overall law-making process.

The deliberative democracy model developed by Jurgen Habermas is an adequate model in explaining the meaning of democratic control through public opinion. This public opinion can become the majority opinion that claims their legitimacy [13]. Deliberative democracy wants to increase the intensity of citizen participation in the process of forming aspirations and opinions so that the policies and

laws produced by the ruling party are closer to the expectations of the governed party. The intensification of the deliberation process through public discourse is a way to realize the concept of Regierung der Regierten democracy (government by the governed) [14]. Merging with the diction 'democracy' gives a special meaning to the concept of democracy. As a concept of 'deliberative democracy' implies a practical discourse, the formation of political opinions and aspirations (politische meinungs und wille bildung), proceduralism or popular sovereignty as a procedure (volksourveranitat als verfahren) [15]. This theory presents questions related to political decisions taken and under what conditions the rules are produced so that in the future citizens comply with these rules. In short, the deliberative democracy model is a model related to the validity of these collective decisions [16]. This model teaches that political decisions must be publicly tested so that the reasons can be accepted by all citizens and do not shy away from criticism and necessary revisions. The more open it is to public space, the more legitimacy the policies or political decisions are made. proceduralism or popular sovereignty as a procedure (volksourveranitat als verfahren) [15]. This theory presents questions related to political decisions taken and under what conditions the rules are produced so that in the future citizens comply with these rules. In short, the deliberative democracy model is a model related to the validity of these collective decisions [16]. This model teaches that political decisions must be publicly tested so that the reasons can be accepted by all citizens and do not shy away from criticism and necessary revisions. The more open it is to public space, the more legitimacy the policies or political decisions are made. This theory presents questions related to political decisions taken and under what conditions the rules are produced so that in the future citizens comply with these rules. In short, the deliberative democracy model is a model related to the validity of these collective decisions [16]. This model teaches that political decisions must be publicly tested so that the reasons can be accepted by all citizens and do not shy away from criticism and necessary revisions. The more open it is to public space, the more legitimacy the

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In a deliberative democracy all types of discourse are practically used in the formation of democratic opinions and aspirations. This is stated by Habermas that the type of practical discourse is pragmatic discourse (pragmatic cher discourse). Pragmatic discourse rests on the fact that the collective goals to be realized have already been determined. The community or part of the community already knows what they want to do, meaning that the community's aspirations have been formed. Therefore, pragmatic legitimacy can only be achieved within the framework of goals that have been accepted and one has only to choose the means to manifest these goals [17].

C. Beginner Selector

Definition of novice voters: Law no. 10 of 2008 in Chapter IV article 19 paragraphs 1 and 2 and article 20 [18] states that what is meant by first-time voters are Indonesian citizens who on election day or voting are Indonesian citizens who are already 17 years old and or more or have/ever married who has the right to vote, and previously was not a voter because of the provisions of the Election Law. As part of the nation's components, youth cannot escape and avoid politics. Human nature, including youth, is a zoon politicon or political being. The existence and progress of youth is part of a political product and is involved either directly or indirectly, real or not real in political life.

Beginner voters consisting of students, university students or voters with an age range of 17-21 years are a truly unique segment, often causing surprises and of course promising in quantity. It is called unique, because the behavior of 21 novice voters with high enthusiasm, is relatively more rational, thirsty for change and less polluted by pragmatism. Beginner voters, especially teenagers (17 years old) have cultural values that are relaxed, free, and tend to things that are informal and seek fun, therefore all things that are not fun will be avoided. Besides seeking pleasure, peer groups are the most important in the life of a teenager, so for a teenager it is necessary to have their own group of friends in association. The Concept of Beginner Voters Voters are Indonesian citizens who are 17 years of age or older or have/have been married. Voters in each general election are registered through data collection carried out by officials appointed by the general election organizers. Beginner voters are voters who vote for the first

time because they are just entering the age of voters, namely 17 to 21 years.

Their knowledge of elections is not much different from other groups, what differs is a matter of enthusiasm and preference. Voters in this case can be constituents or society in general. Constituents are groups of people who feel represented by an ideology that is manifested in political institutions such as political parties. According to Law no. 10 of 2008 in Chapter IV article 19 paragraphs 1 and 2 and article 20 states that what is meant by first-time voters are Indonesian citizens who on election day or voting are Indonesian citizens who are already 17 years old and older or have/have been married who have the right to vote, and previously were not included as voters because of the provisions of the Election Law. According to Suhartono (2009), Beginner voters, especially teenagers, have cultural values that are relaxed, free, and tend to things that are informal and looking for fun, therefore all things that are less fun will be avoided. Besides seeking pleasure, peer groups are the most important thing in a teenager's life, so for a teenager it is necessary to have their own group of friends in association.

So far, novice voters in democratic rituals (legislative elections, presidential elections) have been objects of political activity, namely those who still need guidance and development towards growing their potential and abilities to an optimal level in order to play a role in politics. In the General Election Commission module (2010) first time voters are voters who are going to use their right to vote for the first time, aged 17-21 years. Beginner voters consist of people who have met the requirements to vote, have been registered through data collection carried out by officials appointed by the general election organizers. Their knowledge of elections is not much different from other groups, what differs is their interest and concern about politics.

Regarding the education of novice voters, it has also been regulated in KPU RI Regulation No. 10 of 2018 article 15 concerning Voter Education, namely (1) Voter Education Targets include: a. family; b. Beginner voter; c. Young voters; d. female voters; e. Voters with disabilities; f. Voters with special needs; g. marginalized people; h. community; i. religious; j. democracy volunteers; and/or k. internet citizens (netizens). - 16 (2) Voter Education can be done, through: a. Social Mobilization; b. use of social networks; c. local or traditional media; d. Election Smart House; e. forming a community that cares about elections and democracy; f. forming agents or volunteers for democracy; and/or g. other forms that make the goals of Voter Education achieved. (3) In carrying out Voter Education as referred to in paragraph (1), Provincial KPU/KIP Aceh and Regency/Municipal KPU/KIP can cooperate with: a. community groups or organizations; b. community community; c. religious organizations; d. indigenous groups; e. educational institutions; f. government agencies; g. State Owned Enterprises and Regional Owned Enterprises; and/or h. print and electronic mass media [19].

III. METHOD

Then related to the research method the research approach used in this study is a mixed methods approach [20], namely a mixed quantitative and qualitative research method. Mixed Methods Research is a research design that is based on philosophical assumptions as well as the inquiry method. The mixed methods strategy chosen is a sequential mixed methods strategy where it is necessary to combine or expand findings obtained from quantitative data and findings from qualitative data [21]. This mixed method research method was chosen based on a pragmatic perspective as stated by Creswell [22]. The view of pragmatism is born from actions, situations and consequences that already exist, not from previous conditions. This view rests on the applications and solutions to existing problems [23]. In connection with the theme of this research, the reality that in Indonesia, first-time voters become swing voters, and the results of previous research illustrate a lack of understanding about politics (democracy and the importance of elections).) which leads to a high percentage of abstentions, this requires a solution. So the results of this study can present a solution to the political education model to overcome this problem. the reality that in Indonesia, first-time voters become swing voters, and the results of previous research illustrate a lack of understanding about politics (democracy and the importance of elections) which results in a high percentage of abstentions, this requires a solution. So the results of this study can present a solution to the political education model to overcome this problem. the reality that in Indonesia, first-time voters become swing voters, and the results of previous research illustrate a lack of understanding about politics (democracy and the importance of elections) which results in a high percentage of abstentions, this requires a solution. So the results of this study can present a solution to the political education model to overcome this problem.

The research location was chosen based on a purposive principle, namely Batu City, which was chosen to represent the Greater Malang area which is a city of education and democracy developing along with Batu City becoming an administrative city.

The sampling technique used in the survey as a quantitative method using quota sampling is a technique where the population size is not taken into account. The number determined is 75 respondents from each school so that the total number is 150 respondents, namely students aged between 17-21 years but who return 146 questionnaires. For qualitative research, the research subjects were determined based on a purposive principle, namely the research subjects appointed for the first time by MP Sociology teachers, each of 2 (two) people.

Data collection techniques, are questionnaires using google form, interviews and equipped with Focus Group Discussion (FGD). The questionnaire in the form of a Google form contains questions related to how far the respondent's knowledge of political knowledge includes the notion of the state, democracy, people, ideology, political

education and citizenship, participation of first time voters in the election of members of the legislature and/or presidential election. Online Focus Group Discussions (FGD) were carried out using the zoom platform by presenting two Sociology teachers from State Aliyah Madrasah (MAN) Kota Batu and Public Senior High School (SMAN) II Batu as well as 4 students from the two schools. The interviews were carried out online by involving two Sociology undergraduate students as interviewers.

At this stage, a mixed method data analysis process was used, namely (1) the data reduction stage, reducing quantitative data for interviews (explorative factor analysis) and qualitative data (exploratory thematic analysis); (2) Data Display, namely reducing quantitative data (in the form of tables) and qualitative data in the form of charts or rubrics; (3) Data transformation, namely qualifying and or identifying data (analysis of exploitative factors); (4) Data correlation, namely correlating quantitative data with qualitative data; (5) Data consolidation, namely combining both types of data to create a series of new or integrated data; (6) Comparison of Data namely comparing data from different data sources; (7). Data integration is merging all data into one integrated set of totality or two separate integrated totality sets. The sequential mixed analysis was determined, that is, the analysis was carried out sequentially, first analyzing quantitative data, then analyzing qualitative data. [22]

IV. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

A. Research Result

➤ Description of the Stone Town Region

Batu City before becoming an autonomous region was an Administrative City part of the Malang Regency area. Since the beginning of the reform era, the spirit of autonomy has begun to grow from the people of Batu City in order to maximize development in Batu City itself. One of the first steps taken was to separate itself from Malang Regency so that development activities and exploration of the potentials that existed in Batu City could be carried out intensively, which in the end was to further improve the welfare of the people of Batu City. The establishment of Batu City based on Law Number 11 of 2001, concerning the Establishment of Batu City, consists of 3 (three) District areas, namely: Batu District, Bumiaji District and Junrejo District. Geographically Batu City is located between 7044'.55.11" to 8026'.35, 45" South Latitude and 122017'.10.90" to 122057'.00.00" East Longitude, with an area of 199,087 km² or 19,908.72 hectares (based on the calculation results of the 2001 Bakosurtanal map). The boundaries of Batu City are as follows: (a) To the south are Dau District and Wagir District; (b) To the west is Pujon District; (c) To the east are Karangploso District and Dau District; and (d) North side is Mojokerto Regency and Prigen District. (c) To the east are Karangploso District and Dau District; and (d) North side is Mojokerto Regency and Prigen District. (c) To the east are Karangploso District and Dau District; and (d) North side is Mojokerto Regency and Prigen District.

Batu City has an area of 202,800 Km² which is divided into 3 (three) District areas consisting of 19 (nineteen) Villages and 4 (four) Kelurahan. Of the three sub-districts in Batu City, Bumiaji District has the most extensive land, namely 127,979 Km², while the other sub-districts, namely Batu District and Junrejo District, have an area of 45,248 Km² and 25,650 Km² respectively. Furthermore, economic activity will greatly affect the growth and development of a city. Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP) is one of the indicators to realize development in the physical field of the city. The largest GRDP of Batu City comes from the agricultural and tourism sectors. Another sector which is the leading sector for the economy of Batu City is the trade, hotel and restaurant sector. Along with the climate, With the type of soil and the abundant availability of water in Batu City, the agricultural sector has the potential to be developed, especially horticulture for fruit, vegetable, medicinal plants, ornamental flower plants and so on. The results of this commodity are used to serve the surrounding areas (such as Malang, Surabaya, Kediri, Jombang). In addition, it also has the potential for animal husbandry activities (cows, chickens and goats) as well as tourism potential. The potential of existing horticultural crops also has high commercial value when packaged into agro-tourism, agro-industry and agribusiness. So that tourism packaging based on horticultural agricultural production is a capital for the development of the people's economy in Batu City. In addition to tourism development based on horticultural agriculture, Batu City is rich in natural tourism potential, especially mountain tourism with adventure and sports tourism activities, hot springs and natural scenery, as well as natural conditions that can be packaged into recreational tourism such as the existence of waterfalls and rural tourism related to rural livelihoods/social culture and agriculture . The existence of the industry, especially the handicraft industry based on agricultural production, is a carrying capacity in supporting tourist attractions other than nature tourism. Based on the results of the year-end population registration, the population of Batu City in 2005 was recorded at 170,697 people with a density of 857 people/km. The composition of the population by sex shows that 50.02 percent are male and 49.98 percent are female with a sex ratio of 100.08 percent.

➤ Description of Batu City Politics

During these two decades, the city of Batu has had 4 mayors who were elected through regional head elections, namely in 2001 -2007, 2007-2012 and 2012-2017 and 2017-2022. In 2019 the number of first-time voters in Batu city reached 153,738 voters. This shows that the younger generation as first-time voters will continue to increase as well as ahead of the next local elections in 2022.

➤ Political Knowledge of Respondents

From the results of surveys and structured interviews, it was obtained an illustration that of the 146 youth/newbie voters in Batu city, the level of political knowledge they had was in the following categories:

Table 1. Knowledge Level of Respondents

Category	F	%
Very high	17	11.64
Tall	47	32,20
Currently	53	36,31
Low	24	16,43
Very low	5	3,42
TOTAL	146	100.00

Data source: Author, 2022

From the table above it can be illustrated that the majority of respondents have moderate to very high knowledge of 80.15%, meaning that the majority of first-time high school voters have adequate knowledge about democracy and the aspects contained therein. The highest level of knowledge of respondents is in the middle order of 36.31%. From the results of interviews about knowledge of politics, namely:

- *"politics is more to the art of leading a person and institution as well as in society and in it also has a role and structure between the chairman and members who aim to seek power"*

It can be seen that politics is understood by students, namely how people carry out leadership with the goal of each member, namely seeking power. Politics is also important in the development of a country towards the prosperity of its people. Thus, the younger generation also needs to be instilled with political education since they are teenagers, because it is when they are teenagers that later knowledge will be brought in determining potential candidates in general elections who can be called first-time voters. In accordance with interviews with students, namely:

- *"I think it's very important because Indonesia also adheres to a democratic system. Like it or not, all policies and authorities in government as well as politics are involved in it".*
- *"It really needs to be applied to us as students at this time also applying political education that is in my school in Man through the election of the Student Council Chair and the unique way in the system is that we also adopt elections conducted by the state by using the ballot box, voting for candidate debates, campaigns."*

Political education is currently obtained through primary and secondary socialization, where socialization is carried out by families and the mass media. The dominant role in obtaining information at this time is the social environment and the mass media.

- *"In my family, political education is not very responsive to current political developments. It's just watching the news on TV, but for an in-depth discussion of political choices, it's not."*
- *"With the development of the media platform at this time does it also affect the level of youth participation in the implementation of elections"*

- *"We can see the development of issues regarding national politics and follow them at all times, both from social media, mass media, moreover, there is anti-abstentions campaign content, campaigns for prospective candidates, we can also select candidates from the media."*

The importance of political education can be seen in the way or behavior of first time voters in using their voting rights. Beginner voters are citizens who exercise their right to vote for the first time which is legal according to the state, namely the age of 17 years.

Table 2 Willingness of First Time Voters to Vote

Category	F	%
Tall	132	90.41
Currently	7	4.79
Low	7	4.79
Amount	146	100

Data source: Author, 2022

The appropriate statement as in Mas Raka's interview regarding the response when exercising his right to vote.

- *"Once in 2020 I took part in participating in the post-conflict local election chosen by the mayor of Malang at that time. What I felt at that time when participating in the post-conflict local election was that I was very grateful, because I had been given the opportunity to exercise my right to vote even though at that time I did not know the information about the candidate."*
- *"Before holding the first election, I tried to find background information on the candidate's background, achievements, contributions before running for office. I saw that. I choose from the individual candidates of each pair of candidates."*

Deliberative democracy emphasizes the importance of public participation which is in the nature of dialogue and synthesis together which aims to seek truth based on facts, caring for the interests of society. Deliberative democracy absorbs the weaknesses of the voting mechanism formed by liberal democracy, placing the majority vote as the party entitled to determine collective action. The goal is to build a domination-free universal consensus, which is the fundamental will for every social relationship. As mentioned earlier, Habermas states a democratic model that allows the people to be involved in the process of making laws and political policies. that is deliberative democracy that guarantees civil society to fully participate in making laws through various kinds of discourse. Public participation in the life of the state is very important. This role can only be fulfilled if there is a good connection between the community and the leader. The state must be able to provide space for the community to contribute.

- *"As a student and the younger generation, I don't really respond because I know my capacity is only as a student and I don't have the authority to criticize programs that don't work, because I feel that if I'm too critical, it's not certain that the rulers who run their government can*

receive a response from I, in my opinion, as a citizen or the people, please understand that the candidates will not forget the proker when it comes to election time because promises must be kept and leadership must also be accounted for not only to the people but God too."

- "In my opinion, at the moment, I think that political parties are still far away from achieving a clean and fair democracy, yes, because there are many chronological cases of events, people who should be given the freedom to express opinions, issue critical ideas, there are still those who are suppressed, silenced by the authorities, and are considered rebels. and so on, even though we as a society must also have an obligation to monitor, supervise government performance"
- "I have great hope for the youth, let's use your right to vote, because starting from ourselves determining the right to vote, using our right to vote for the benefit of society which is useful for finding leaders who are truly able to answer the trust of the community."

➤ Political Education Expected by Beginner Voters

The description of political education expected by respondents as first-time voters is:

- Education that teaches justice and government and community counseling
- Political education is carried out openly, either in the school environment or the general public. Such as political education seminars, questions and answers or discussions about politics. Because not a few young people care less about politics and think that politics is something that makes you dizzy and doesn't need to think about it. In the future, it is hoped that there will be social activities that can change this mindset.
- Ideal political education is a way that is built to create a common goal or aspiration and introduces "politics" as the essence of social life but is still oriented to the interests and common good.
- Political education by introducing various correct political understandings without reducing the facts a bit because if there is a reduction it will cause serious problems
- Political education that has good interaction regarding the rights, obligations and responsibilities of every citizen
- Political education by planting positive things
- The ideal political education is political education that is in accordance with the Constitution or in accordance with the ideology of our country
- The ideal political education is to learn the ins and outs of politics and learn the tactics used in the world of politics
- Politics based on tolerance and not harming one another
- Education that includes systems not far from politics and systems in everyday life about politics. But the political education also should not be excessive,
- The ideal political education is one that can explain its system and its functions and parts properly. In the sense that it can provide sufficient material on politics.
- The ideal political education must know the vision and mission in politics, also know what is right and wrong

with certainty also know some of the risks after entering the world of politics.

- Political education is able to change people's mindset and perspective on politics for the better and is able to carry out their rights and obligations as they should
- Education that explains politics as a whole, without interfering with the interests and doctrines of certain parties
- Political education that is simple but can be understood by students

In addition, the expectations of first-time voters regarding the political education mechanism expected by 26 respondents (17%) stated that political education for first-time voters needed to involve universities or political institutions. While 68 respondents (46%) stated the need for democratic political education that accommodated the aspirations of voters, 29 respondents (19.86%) could only give it through school and 23 (15.75%) respondents stated that they did not know.

The temporary conclusion from the initial analysis of adequate political knowledge of novice voters is the background for the desire for political education for those who put more emphasis on justice, there is no doctrine or the interests of certain groups, true democracy, enlightens voters, especially about a complete understanding in order to change people's mindsets to be better about the politics needed in social life.

B. Discussion

➤ Deliberative Political Education for Beginner Voters

Political education for novice voters needs to broaden its meaning, not just being tied to elections. Because political education will strengthen one's citizenship. Political education does not only discuss about voting rights but also contributes to the voice in determining who will take office. First, voting rights can be used if citizens are enlightened, have knowledge of their obligations and rights, and can participate in giving aspirations. Direct participation of citizens in government is very possible in a democratic political system. Political participation is carried out not only choosing leaders but also participating in determining public policies and participating in overseeing the political process. Political education makes the point of view of novice voters more critical and rational in determining their choices. Political education can be linked to the political knowledge of novice voters. The results of the study show that the level of political knowledge for first time voters is moderate, a percentage of 36.31% is obtained.

Deliberative political education can also create quality democracy. This statement is believed by Laila Purnawati that political education will shape the value of awareness, rights and responsibilities and the level of education can affect the quality of the human resources themselves. Political education should actually be carried out routinely and transparently, but the fact is that it is not routinely only tucked into Civic Education (PKN) subjects or carried out if there are activities ahead of elections, actors who carry out

political education, namely political parties and KPU in collaboration with schools. Kenneth D Wollack stated that political education helps citizens understand the importance of giving voting rights and procedures in elections and making decisions.

Gieseckle states, as quoted by Kartono (2009) in political education there are several elaborations, namely *bildungswissen*, which is able to distinguish the shape and size of human image and its development so that people become familiar with the personal strengths and abilities of the nation itself, aware of its strengths and advantages.

Our nation. Second, *orientierungswissen*, namely the ability to be oriented towards understanding humanity, objectively having the courage to see the actual reality and wanting to reorient to the political situation so that more alternative solutions can be found. third, *verwaltungs weisen* (referring to behavior), namely understanding the laws, norms, rules and regulations that guide all political behavior, so that individuals become more careful and wise in responding to concrete political conditions. In other words, individuals are able and want to control their own behavior. Adhere to the principles of decency and selflessness.

Fourth, *actionwesen* (1) means the ability to act appropriately, carefully and correctly because it is supported by a principle of truth and justice; (ii) Education is accompanied by objective reasoning; and (3) critical insight. The principles of truth and justice must be universal. Thinking contains the ability to think well and be able to think again about political events so that reflective monitoring takes place and generates ideas for them to solve problems through conscience and political moral responsibility towards our fellow human beings we will develop the courage to act and respond appropriately.

The reality that occurs in society, democratic politics is full of uncertainty. This assumption departs from the fact that democracy has this manifested in the form of freedom to form political parties, direct elections for president and vice president, and elections for regional heads. Deliberative democracy was introduced by Jürgen Habermas, maybe it could be an alternative to answer the question of democracy. This deliberative democracy is not a new pattern in the current form of democracy, for example: Guided Democracy, Pancasila Democracy, and Parliamentary Democracy, but the political model is expected to be able to explain the dynamics of political communication. Habermas sees that communication contained in democracy has not been able to realize it. The communication referred to in this context is communication between the community and leaders. Deliberative democracy by Jürgen Habermas is an intellectual contribution that can be considered to solve today's problems of democracy. depending on deliberative democracy requires communication between society and the state which is termed public space.

The results of the study show that education carried out in schools has a public space in the form of freedom such as determining class presidents, organizational structure and selecting extracurriculars and determining student council presidents and deputy chairmen, but in practice it is still considered ineffective, according to Mas Raka's statement during the FGD .

- *"We are aware that we, as the millennial generation, get political education only in PKN lessons. That's not what it is, it's something that is practical but just a concept, so maybe we can get that education from information on social media. Meanwhile, on social media, what we hear about politics is something dirty, something that is not true. So that, in my opinion, is the importance of politics for youth, especially the millennial generation. As Mrs. Vina said earlier, it's important, as a school, it can't just be a school that provides political education, you have to invite other institutions that are more competent to provide a little knowledge or understanding about understanding. Earlier maybe in the future if you can work together with outside agencies in a school "*

Beginner voters generally do not have experience in exercising their right to vote in general elections (elections). They need to know and understand various things related to elections, for example: (1) reasons for holding elections; (2) stages of election implementation; (3) actors who can participate and take part in elections; And (4) regarding the procedures for first-time voters in using their right to vote in elections. This is important for young people, in this case students or the younger generation, to become intelligent millennial voters, to make political choices in every election.

Beginner voters basically have dynamic thoughts, do not yet have a strong foundation. This could happen because novice voters are citizens in the youth category who are still looking for their true identity to be able to join or exercise their voting rights. Most novice voters use voting rights because they see profiles and follow the choices of their parents or friends. Efforts were made to introduce politics through the election of the chairperson and vice chairman of the osis which uses a system as similar as possible to general elections.

The simulation used in the school environment, namely the election of student council presidents and representatives which is made similar to elections, there are several aspects that are used. (1) instilling an understanding of what a general election / osis election is. (2) understanding in the process of organizing elections. (3) Education on how to use the right to vote. (4) education on how to determine the right candidate or before determining. (5) education regarding the potential for fraud that often occurs. The importance of the education described above is because so far the practice of selecting student councils is that students choose based on appearance without considering the experience that has been done. According to the statement from Ms. Maysita and Ms. Riska.

- *"In my experience, once some students chose him not based on the experience of the candidate but based on their physique, from their beauty, from their handsomeness."*
- *"In my opinion, the education of novice voters is very important. Because in an era like this what Mas Raka has said. We as the younger generation of this golden generation will later become supporters, where our voice is the benchmark for children whether or not this can be implemented in politics, because we are also the ones who elect the people's representatives so we have to be careful too. Because yes, what we know about politics is not purely clean."*

The research conducted shows that it turns out that students understand very well what elections really are that are important to do. In fact, a lack of understanding about the urgency of elections is dangerous for the implementation of democracy in a country because of the impact on students' interest in participating in elections. They also do not know if the votes they cast in elections are very meaningful for the political process in their country. In addition, only a portion of the students understand the stages and procedures for selection. While others don't, they don't have experience voting in elections, in fact they are often reluctant to participate in elections and choose to go along with them and don't want to use their right to vote or abstain. While some others even admit that they don't know who the candidate is and what party they are.

Elections ?. Shows that the level of interest of novice voters to participate in elections is from very high to very low categories, as shown in the following table:

Table 3 Participation in the Use of Voting Rights.

Category	F	%
Very high	18	12,32
Tall	29	19.86
Currently	36	24,66
Low	49	33,56
Very low	14	9.60
TOTAL	146	100.00

Data source: Author, 2022

The data shows that the interest in participating in the first election is in the very high to moderate category of 56.84, while the low to very low category is 43.16%. This shows that there are still novice voters who are reluctant to use their right to vote because the candidates are indecisive and don't have enough knowledge in the novice election. Beginner voters looking for information regarding any party and who is a candidate through social media. The use of applications on social media is not only used to communicate but also to add information about the world of politics, especially elections. This is in accordance with the results of research conducted on novice voters such as the results of student interviews;

- *"It is true that it is very influential if the current digital footprint is very fast, we can see the development of issues regarding national politics and we follow them at*

any time, both from social media, mass media, moreover, there is content for anti-abstentions campaigns, campaigns for prospective candidates, we can also select candidates. from the media".

Utilization of social media applications is used to find information by accessing a variety of applications available on social media. The reality in society, especially among students or students, is that they use various social media applications. Beginner voters among students have the majority view of the urgency of social media which is used as a socialization tool for cadres or legislative candidates so that they can know the vision, mission and work programs that they can later make as smart and careful decisions in selecting the candidates nominated. .

Table 4 Information Obtained From the Media

Category	F	%
Very high	49	33,56
Tall	36	24,66
Currently	29	19.86
Low	18	12,32
Very low	14	9.60
TOTAL	146	100.00

Data source: Author, 2022

Advances in information technology are increasingly developing, making it easier for people to get information. Beginner voters think that this has become a trend among politicians to disseminate information to the public, especially first-time voters regarding elections or political knowledge. With advances in technology, novice voters among students are more effective through social media. This is understandable because it is in accordance with the spirit of today's young generation who prefer practicality, it is easy to get information by accessing the internet anywhere and anytime.

V. CONCLUSION

From the results of this study it can be concluded that the political knowledge of novice voters in Batu city is sufficient. This is the background for the desire for political education for those who place more emphasis on justice, no doctrine or interests of certain groups, true democracy, enlightens voters, especially about a complete understanding. for the sake of changing the mindset of society to be better about the politics needed in social life. The results of this study also resulted in a new policy principle (novelty) that had never existed before, namely an invention (invention), namely a political education model of deliberative democracy based on local wisdom for novice voters, namely political education that teaches students knowledge about deliberative democracy based on local wisdom values. . Democracy that truly involves the aspirations of the younger generation to improve the quality of the implementation of governance or the running of legislative institutions at the local, regional and national levels. The results of this study need to be developed further, especially at the level of applying the political education model for first-time voters that has been produced

above. The application of this model can be tried out in several schools in districts/cities in East Java province.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Student Person. (2020). 10 Most Populous Countries in the World (2020). <https://www.top10.id/10-country-with-penresident-of-the-most-di-dunia/>
- [2]. Indonesian Survey Institute. (2019). The lowest number of abstentions in the 2019 presidential election since 2004. BBC News Indonesia, <https://www.bbc.com/indonesia/indonesia-48130161>
- [3]. Detik news. October 6 (2020). Prediction of the Number of Beginner Voters in 2024. Error! Hyperlink references are not valid. news/d-5202312/kpu-number-of-starter-voters-in-the-2020-elections-increase
- [4]. Luckily, Jackie. (2014). Political Participation of Beginner Voters in the Election of Regent and Deputy Regent in Talaud District (A Study in South Essang District, Talaud District). *POLITICO Journal of Political Science*. Matter. 58-62
- [5]. Uung Sendana (2020). <https://.kompas.com/read/2020/06/11/16213721/-sara-divalu-masih-jadi-persoalan-di-indonesia>.
- [6]. Papuan violence. <https://nasional.kompas.com/read/2020/06/11/16213721/isu-sara-divalu-masih-jadi-persoalan-di-indonesia>.
- [7]. Soedarwo and Wahyudi, (2015). "An Integrative-Participative Model for Strengthening National Knowledge and Political Education to Cadres and Constituents of Political Parties". *Research on Humanities and Social Sciences*. www.iiste.org ISSN (Paper)2224-5766 ISSN (Online)2225-0484 (Online) Vol.5, No.8.
- [8]. Soedarwo, Vina SD (2019). "A Political Education Model of Political Parties in Indonesia". *International Journal of Humanities Social Science and Education (IJHSSE)*. Volume 6, Issue 9, September 2019, PP 134-140 ISSN 2349-0373 (Print) & ISSN 2349-0381 (Online) <http://dx.doi.org/10.20431/2349-0381.0609015>
- [9]. Fernanda. (2016). Beginner Voters' Perceptions of Simultaneous Local Elections in Way Mili Village
- [10]. <https://www.neliti.com/publications/252582/persepsi-pelecer-pemula-terhadap-pilkada-serentak-di-desa-way-mili>
- [11]. Hajad & Ikhsan (2019). Political Education for Beginner Voters at SMAN 1 Meureubo, West Aceh District. *Community Service Journal: Darma Bakti Teuku Umar*, 1(1), 19. <https://doi.org/10.35308/baktiku.v1i1.1237>
- [12]. Ratnamulyani & Mintai, (2018). The Role of Social Media in Increasing Beginner Voter Participation Among Students in Bogor District. *Sociohumanities*, 20(2), 154–161. <https://doi.org/10.24198/sosiohumaniora.v20i2.13965>.
- [13]. Angelia, N., Sembiring, WM, Hidayat, TW, & Matondang, A. (2019). Youth Voter Political Education to Increase Rights Participation Choose in General Elections. *International Journal of Humanities, Social Sciences and Education*, 6(7), 121–125. <https://doi.org/10.20431/2349-0381.0607013>
- [14]. Hardiman, F. Budi. (2009). *Deliberative Democracy; Considering the rule of law and public space in Jurgen Habermas's Discourse Theory*. Sleman: PT. Canisius. matter. 128.
- [15]. Hardiman, F. Budi. (2009). *Deliberative Democracy; Considering the rule of law and public space in Jurgen Habermas's Discourse Theory*. Sleman: PT. Canisius. matter. 126.
- [16]. Hardiman, F. Budi. (2009). *Deliberative Democracy; Considering the rule of law and public space in Jurgen Habermas's Discourse Theory*. Sleman: PT. Canisius. matter. 128.
- [17]. Hardiman, F. Budi. (2009). *Deliberative Democracy; Considering the rule of law and public space in Jurgen Habermas's Discourse Theory*. Sleman: PT. Canisius. matter. 129.
- [18]. Hardiman, F. Budi. (2009). *Deliberative Democracy; Considering the rule of law and public space in Jurgen Habermas's Discourse Theory*. Sleman: PT. Canisius. p..115.
- [19]. UU no. 10 of 2008. <https://www.google.com/search?q=understanding+voters+beginners+according+to+undangundag&oq=definition+pickers+beginners&aqs=chrome.3.69i57j0i19i22i30l4.7216j0j7&sourceid=chrome&ie=UTF-8>
- [20]. RI KPU Regulation No 10 of 2018. https://jdih.kpu.go.id/data/data_pkpu/PKPU%2010%20TAHUN%202018.pdf
- [21]. Brannen, Yulia. (Ed.). (1995). *Mixing Methods: Qualitative and Quantitative Research*. Aldershot: Avebury.
- [22]. Creswell, John. W. (2012). *Research Design; Qualitative, Quantitative and Mixed Approaches*. Yogyakarta: Student Library.p.22.
- [23]. Creswell, John. W. (2012). *Research Design; Qualitative, Quantitative and Mixed Approaches*. Translated by Achmad Fawaid. Yogyakarta: Student Libraries. pg 15.
- [24]. Patton, MQ (1990). *Qualitative Evaluation and Research Methods (2nd Edition)*. Translated by Achmad Fawaid. Newbury Park. CA: Sage.
- [25]. Tashakkori & Teddlie. (2010). *Handbook of Mixed Methods; in Social and Behavioral Research*. Daryatno's translation. Yogyakarta: Student Libraries. matter. 337.
- [26]. Beginner voters in Batu City will increase by 153,738 to take part in the 2019 elections. Error! Hyperlink references are not valid. [/read/182531/20181112/212800/beginner-in-town-batu-increasing-153-738-will-take-in-2019-election](https://read/182531/20181112/212800/beginner-in-town-batu-increasing-153-738-will-take-in-2019-election)
- [27]. Kartini Kartono. (2009). *Political Education Part of Adult Education*.
- [28]. Bandung : Mamdar Maju